

A Study on Effectiveness Training and Development at Solara Active Pharma Science Limited Puducherry

Jaya Priya, Aravindasamy

MBA Student, Rajiv Gandhi College of Engineering and Technology, Puducherry, India

ABSTRACT

Training and Development is a subsystem of an organisation which emphasizes on the improvement of the performances of individual and groups. Training is an educational process which involves the sharpening of reaction, learning, behavior and results which enhances the performances of the employees. The objective of the study is to find the level of effectiveness of training and development in Solara Active Pharma Science and to find the association between effectiveness of training and development and job performance. The total population of the study is 120 and the sample size is 60, simple random sampling technique were used for the study. Through questionnaire, primary data was collected and by referring books and journals, secondary data was collected. The researcher used Chi-square test to find the effectiveness of training and development. From the study it was found that the Effectiveness of Training and Development at Solara Active Pharma Science Ltd is moderate and there is no association between effectiveness of training and development and job performance.

KEYWORDS: Training, of reaction, learning, behavior, effectiveness of training, training and development, job performance

INTRODUCTION

Training is said to be the acquisition of knowledge of skills, and the competencies. It has specific goals of improving one's knowledge, skills and their capacity, capability, performance and their productivity. It is said that observers of labour market has clearly mentioned, more than initial qualifications for a work, to upgrade and update skills. Vigorous training and development should be three in the organization. Thus the training and development is the branch of human resource function. It is said that only training & development is much important because it leads to a maximum utilization of all the some of firm. Thus the skills which were utilized by the human resource of firm can increase in output, quality improvement at the company. Training & development increase in efficiency, increase of morale of employees, better human relations, reduction in supervision, increased in organizational liability & flexibility (Ganesh, M., & Indradevi, R, 2015).

Training and development are the processes of investing in people so that they are equipped to perform. These processes are part of an overall human resource management approach that hope fully will result in people being motivated to perform. It goes without saying therefore that the training and development of employees is an issue that has to be faced by every organization. However, the amount, quality and quantity of training carried out vary enormously from organization to organization. Organizations have to train their employees very well

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(Younas, W., Farooq, M., Khalil-Ur-Rahman, F., & Zreen, A., 2018).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Ganesh M & Dr. R. Indradevi revealed that the paper provides an insight of training and important / effectiveness of training. To make training more effectiveness organization requires to look at those training & development is associated with the particular department managers should first motivate employees to learn acquire new skills & knowledge. To conclude that training & development programme conducted in the University was found to be good and the same may be said if it enhance its training development programme based on the above finding. Suggestion it would help employees. Different level of training is to be kept to different level of man power. Since employees in an organization will be able to perform their duties and can make meaningful contribution to the success to the organization goals. The study intends to carry the work further with larger number of respondents, may be with a wider frame. There is a document evident that training activities have a positive impact on the performance of the individuals and the teams. Training activities can also be beneficial other than the individual and the team level.

Mpofu, M., & Hlatywayo, C. K. revealed that to improve employee training and development in the municipality, and improved performance and service delivery, management

should increase the number of employees taking part in training and development. This can be done by providing incentives that may motivate employees to take part in training and development programs. Incentives that could motivate employees to take part in employee training and development include the prospect of promotion or the provision of clear hierarchies in the organization so as to indicate where performance is rewarded. The possibility of a salary increase can also be used as a motivating factor to encourage employees to take part in employee training and development programs. Access to and transfer of information on employee training and development programs can be improved by the responsible authorities, within the municipality.

Nda, M. M., & Fard, R. Y. revealed that the Training and development ultimately upgrade not only the productivity of employees but also of the organization. It has rightly been said, employee development is the key to organizational sustainable development. Organizations must have employees who are able to quickly adapt to an ever-changing world market. Companies need to invest in on-going employee training and development in order to both keep employees and be successful. The 21st century will be favorable to those organizations, which are able to learn faster and adapt to changes than their competitors. Training enhances employees' initiative and quality of work, thereby assisting them to be more committed to achieving the organizational goals and objectives and in turn enhancing employees' effectiveness within the organisation.

Kriemadis, T., & Kourtesopoulou, A. revealed that The present review focused on the type of OMD training method, by analyzing the specific characteristics/nature, the goals (empowerment of leadership skills and teamwork), presenting the main theories and models for the better understanding of the value of the outdoors as a tool for management development and reviewing some impacts and evaluations of such programs.

Vinesh revealed that the companies other than multi-nationals are not meeting the employee demands with reference to training and development and ultimately the gaps found in the required skills vis-a-vis attained skills have become so wide that inter-relationships of training and performance are badly disturbed. There is still a big gap between the knowledge and skills imparted and acquired in the institutions and its applications as seen in the industrial environments. Due to this gap, companies now feel that there should be a close liaison between such institutions and the industry so that employee development programs are made more purpose oriented. There are training institutions which offer customized as well as off-the-shelf programs based on their client's business operations but yet, there is much to be improved

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To find the level of effectiveness of training and development in the company Solara Active Phrama Science.
2. To find the association between effectiveness of training and development and job performance

HYPOTHESIS:

1. H₀: There is no association between effectiveness of training and development and job performance
2. H_a: There is an association between of training and development and job performance

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Researcher used descriptive study and it was based on primary data and secondary data. Through questionnaire primary data was collected and by referring books, journals and company records secondary data was collected. The study as total population of 120 and the sample size is 60, it used simple random sampling. The study used statically tool like Chi-square to get the result.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Chart 1 showing the level of effectiveness of training and development

SOURCE: Primary Source

INFERENCE:

The above score chat has been framed from the questionnaire. The questionnaire consists of 13 question relating to effectiveness of Training and development. The score for each question on the questionnaire range from 1 to 5. Hence the maximum score is 65 and minimum score is 13. From the above chart it is seen that 40.2 is the score for Effectiveness of Training and Development which indicate moderate level.

The table 1 showing the analysis using chi-square test

Job performances Training and development	LOW	MODERATE	HIGH
LOW	0	0	0
MODERATE	9	36	12
HIGH	0	1	2

SOURCE: Primary Source

INFERENCE

Since the calculated value of $\chi^2(3.426) >$ the table value (0.489) of χ^2 , H₀ is rejected. Therefore, there is a no association between effectiveness of training and development and job performance.

FINDINGS

1. The level of Effectiveness of Training and Development at Solara Active Pharma Science ltd is moderate.
2. By using chi square test, it was found that there is no association between effectiveness of training and development and job performance.

SUGGESTIONS

On the basis of the results found from the survey taken on Solara active pharma Science Ltd leads to some of the following suggestions. These suggestions are given with account of the improving the standard of the company.

1. The organization should provide necessary training program employee
2. The organization should provide skilled trainer's to the trainees. So, that the training program will be effective.
3. The organization should take necessary steps to reduced labour turnover and absenteeism.

CONCLUSION

According to Edwin B. Flippo, Training is the art of increasing the knowledge and skills of an employee for doing a particular job. The objective of the study is to find the level of effectiveness of training and development in Solara Active Pharma Science and to find the association between effectiveness of training and development and job performance. From the study it was found that the Effectiveness of Training and Development at Solara Active Pharma Science Ltd is moderate and there is no association between effectiveness of training and development and job performance.

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